

Yoga and Ayurveda

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Abstract—The term Yoga is derived from Sanskrit root “ yuj” meaning to unite ,to combine i.e. union of the individual soul with the cosmic ,Divine or supreme soul or total integration of the physical ,mental,intellectual and the spiritual aspects of the human personality.

Ayurveda is derived from Ayush ved i.e. to know about life. The four principal instincts of life namely Dharm,Artha,Kama,and Moksh .Health is a comprehensive state of wellbeing which refers to a physical,mental,spiritual and intellectual wellbeing of individual.Aim of ayurveda is

Index Terms—yuj, cosmic,devine , Spiritual

I. Introduction

स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणम्,आतुरस्य विकारप्रशमनं च |च.सू.30/26

The utility of Ayurveda is to help maintain the health of a healthy individual.

Living Being has been conceived as a composite entity consisting of a physical body superadded with highly sensitive sense apparatus ,Mind and the soul .According to ayurveda the panchendriyas are not the simple part of body but are considered specialized units which function under the control of the manas and thought which the higher perceptual functions are performed. Ayurveda also includes the elements of the science and philosophy of yoga as may be needed for health and medical science .

Yoga developed originally with the object of utilizing it as a system of medicine or as a health discipline , the persons enlightened through the practice of yoga could enjoy better health and could remain from illness.

Yoga is essential branch of Ayurveda .its objective is not to provide health to achieve all the four instincts of life as mentioned above as in case of ayurveda .Its main emphasis appears to be an achievement of Moksha Though such achievements are primarily spiritual and mental in nature ,the critical study of the contents of the yoga shastra would indicate that Yoga also considers the welfare of health as a whole including physical health because the spiritual developments will necessarily need a healthy body to practice the spiritual sciences.

The study of conceptual tradition of yoga indicates that Yoga is the central theme of Indian Philosophy.The contents of the science of yoga appear to have been extensively dealt with in early Upanishads with further systematization in yoga sutras of Patanjali which presented for the first time the most critical account of the science of yoga in a systemic manner.The Bhagavad Gita appears to have attempted the application of the science of Yoga in the social and personal life of a common

man .A follow up study of the thought on yoga would show that from time to time the enlightened thinkers have attempted to give their own interpretations to the original thoughts of yoga . In modern times certain contemporary thinkers in the field of Indian philosophy have brought revolutionary ideas in this field. The applied thought on Yoga Hindu approach to life presented by Swami Vivekanand ,Sri Arvind and Mahatma Gandhi have brought the fundamentals of Indian philosophy and Yoga much nearer to the reality of man ,life and society .

Ayurveda and yoga both are based on the same fundamental principles and appear to make allied approach. Both believe in the Saddhatwamak nature of the creation and in the four dimensional entity of living being namely -Body, Senses ,Mind and Soul . The harmonious functioning of all these four components of the individual living being is also considered an aspect of Yoga . In Ayurveda, Charak Samhita describes the state of higher achievements of Yoga practice including the ultimate realization under term Satyabuddhi. According To Charakachary the Lok i.e. Universe is saddhatwamak Constituted of five Mahabhutas. And the sixth is the Avyakt Brahma. The same six Dhatus constitute the purush .The realization that the entire universe and individual are one and the same is called satya buddhi. It eliminates all miseries and leads to Moksh .Charakacharya says that selfness is the cause of all miseries. The moment selfness is eliminated ,the great knowledge ,the satya -buddhi represents the same central theme of Yoga as is seen in the core discipline of yoga Traditions. Thus Ayurveda and Yoga are allied science. Ayurveda envisages the total welfare of man, while yoga specially ensures his psycho-spiritual development.

II. Conclusion

As pointed out above Yoga and Ayurveda are not only allied disciplines but are complimentary to each other. It is most appropriate to consider Yoga as a branch of Ayurveda. Ayurveda is complete science of life and is supposed to safeguard health. The main objective of health as conceived in Indian traditions is to achieve the four principal instincts of life Dharma, Artha, Kam, Moksh. In contrast Yoga as understood in the early Upanishadic thought ,is a discipline of more limited objectives and is specially concerned with the achievement of Moksh.

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